

A Study on Different Techniques for Skin Cancer Detection

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Abstract— The number of cases of melanoma skin cancer has been increasing year by year. Skin cancer is one of the most dangerous types of cancer because it's much more likely to spread to other parts of the body if not diagnosed and treated early. About three million people are diagnosed with the disease every year in the United States alone. Early detection of Melanoma skin cancer is very much necessary for the patient for it to be curable. Today's technological advancements can make possible the early detection of skin cancer. As per the literature, the lesion characteristics such as shape, color, structure, etc. are the important parameters for the detection of skin cancer. In this paper, we review the various soft computing and artificial intelligence techniques for early-stage melanoma skin cancer detection.

Keywords— Melanoma, Skin Cancer, Soft Computing, Artificial Intelligence, Neural Networks, Accuracy

I. INTRODUCTION

Melanoma is among the worst forms of skin cancer in individuals, appearing as colored moles or markings on the skin. Melanoma develops whenever someone problem occurs in the cells that produce melanin (melanocytes), which give your skin its color. Fair skin, a history of sunburn, hereditary factors, a compromised immunological system, tanning beds, and high UV radiation are all risk factors for Melanoma.

As per the National Cancer Institute, 87,110 new cases of melanoma were predicted to be detected in 2020, with 11000 people dying from the disease. Melanoma is more than 20 more rapidly in white people than in black people. Generally, whites have a 2.6 percent (1 in 38) lifespan danger of melanoma, blacks have a 0.1 percent (1 in 1,000) lifetime risk, and Hispanics have a 0.58 percent (1 in 172) lifetime risk. Melanoma risk rises as people get older. When people are diagnosed with it, they are on average 63 years old. Melanoma is not uncommon in people under the age of 30.

Melanoma develops and spread over the first layer of skin

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before penetrating deeper layers and eventually coming into touch with lymph veins and blood if it is not detected early. When skin cancer is detected early, it has a better chance of being cured than when it is diagnosed later. Early identification of skin cancer, on the other hand, is a costly endeavor. It's tough to tell if a lesion is benign or cancerous because skin lesions resemble each other so closely. A typical mole is a consistent hue, such as tan, brown, or black, with a distinct border separating it from the outer tissue.

Various non-invasive approaches are being developed to assess the skin sore and identify it as benign or melanoma. Image capture, pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification are all being evaluated with the aim of using the feature values to determine which type of skin cancer it is. These methods have proven to be more effective, less unpleasant, and less costly than traditional clinical diagnostic methods. In the next sections, we'll go through several modern techniques that use different algorithms to diagnose skin cancer accurately.

Figure 1: Skin Cancer Prediction Model

A. Stages of Skin Cancer Detection

Input Skin Image: The image was taken from a skin cancer database. In the general subject of dermatology, there are very few information sets and even fewer datasets of skin sore photographs. Furthermore, the vast majority of these databases are either insufficient or not readily accessible, posing an additional barrier to conducting a systematic investigation in the area.

Pre-processing: A essential action to deal with images that aren't of good enough quality to be analyzed. This lack of value could be due to the presence of antiquities (e.g., hair) nearby, which could have a negative impact on the display of the subsequent steps.

Feature Extraction: A crucial step in creating a realistic portrayal of skin lesions. Tracking correct features is a difficult task, but a great deal of study has been done in this area, making it possible to discern a wide range of highlights that depict skin lesions.

Classification: The classification phase is the final step in the diagnosis. A classification-based method can be used to identify the type of cancer. Due to the general substantial amount of danger associated with the earlier type of malignancy, the most of CAD systems focus on distinguishing between melanoma and kind or atypical nevi. However, it is also possible to develop CAD systems that focus on detecting melanocytic and non-melanocytic injuries, as well as differentiating other types of skin disease. For one of the machine learning techniques, a few classifiers were used.

II. RELATED WORK

A. ABCD Rule-Based Detection

In this paper [9], Hardian et.al uses the ABCD rule of dermoscopy for extracting the skin lesion. A smartphone camera is used to capture the lesion image and this image is processed by using the ABCD rule. Feature extraction is performed on the pre-processed image where the four features - Asymmetry (A), Border (B), Color(C), and D (Diameter) are extracted in the following way. 1) Asymmetry – Melanoma lesions are asymmetric in nature. The asymmetry index is used for determining the level of symmetry of the object. This is done by dividing the image horizontally or vertically. 2) Border - In the case of melanoma, the border is irregular, ragged, and blurred. The compactness index is used to determine border irregularity. 3)Color – Melanoma is not uniform in color, unlike benign mole. Normalized Euclidean distance between each pixel is used to determine the color uniformity. 4) Diameter - The melanoma lesion has larger than 6 mm. The diameter in the

image is found and compared to the 6mm measurement.

The major drawbacks of the proposed method are:

1) According to [4], in order to analyze the ABCD score, the criteria are assigned semi-quantitatively. Each of the criteria is then multiplied by a given weight factor to calculate a total dermoscopy score. The ABCD rule works appropriately for thin melanocytic wounds. The ABCD rule has about 59% to 88% accuracy in diagnosing melanoma, but biopsy is needed for a more precise diagnosis.

2) According to [10], the ABCD method, in some cases, isn't helpful to classify malignant and benign skin moles. In addition, the method may not recognize some malignant moles at early stages, for example malignant melanoma with a small diameter than 6mm. This poses the challenge of differentiating malignant melanoma and birthmarks

B. Backpropagation Neural Networks based diagnosis

In this paper, Pratik et al. [3] propose the use of the ABCD rule for extracting features and a backpropagation neural network to classify the lesions as melanoma or benign. The criteria that combine to create the ABCD rule of dermoscopy are asymmetry, border, color, and diameter. In this paper, they have extracted the features based on the ABCD rule after successful segmentation. As the number of classes increases, it becomes difficult to classify lesions into their appropriate classes accurately. Neural Networks inherently possess a better capability of handling complex relationships between different parameters. Thus, the proposed model makes use of Backpropagation neural networks. However, the proposed method as certain drawbacks. The major drawbacks of this method are slow convergence rates and trapping in local minima. According to [4] the backpropagation algorithm is known as a local search algorithm which uses gradient descent to iteratively develop the weights and biases in the neural network

C. Hybrid artificial neural network and world cup optimization

NavidRazmjoooy et al. [4] have proposed a new hybrid algorithm between the artificial neural network and world cup optimization for enhancing the back-propagation algorithm efficiency and for escaping from trapping in the local minima. The world cup optimization (WCO) algorithm has been used to help ANN to find the initial optimal weights in the back-propagation algorithm, to speed up the convergence speed, and minimize the root mean square error between the actual output and the target output. In the WCO algorithm, the best teams from each group arise to the next level and the rest are eliminated. They have used the same concept in the Backpropagation algorithm to search around the best cost for some epochs and if the search result is better than the best cost, the output will be achieved; otherwise, the

previous output will be selected. The biggest advantage of the proposed method is the use of world cup optimization to resolve the drawbacks of the backpropagation algorithm.

D. Hybrid genetic algorithm- Artificial Neural Network

In this paper [7], Aswin et al. present a computer-aided approach to skin cancer detection. The steps involved are 1) image processing 2) segmentation 3) feature extraction and 4) classification. The Image processing step includes image resizing and image hair removal using dull razor software, which is free medical imaging software. Even though the proposed model makes use of an efficient software tool, the paper neglects the negative effects that the tool may have. The software makes use of a mean filter effectively. smoothens the hair in the images; however, in this process, it may smoothens the edges and thus compromise the quality of the image. The next step involves segmentation using the open-source ImageJ software. However, the author of the paper ignores the fact that the ImageJ software has certain drawbacks. The major drawback is that if you're going to deal with large stacks of images, you may bump up against problems in the default memory configuration for the program. The Otsu color thresholding which is a simple yet powerful thresholding technique is employed in this paper. The threshold level is set such that the background skin pixels are removed and only the foreground lesion remains.

The major drawback of thresholding methods, according to [8] is that they can achieve good results only if there is a high contrast between the lesion area and the surrounding skin region, which may not always be the case.

They have then used GLCM for feature extraction and to obtain the features, namely Contrast, Correlation, Homogeneity, and Energy. The selected features are given as input to the classifier which classifies the images as cancerous or non-cancerous. The proposed system for feature extraction makes use of the fact that Malignant melanoma has a mix of red, green, and dark coloration whereas benign lesion has a uniform color pattern.

Finally, the Classification is done using a hybrid Genetic algorithm – An artificial neural network classifier. A conventional ANN classifier uses a backpropagation algorithm for training. However, the major drawback of this conventional technique is that the solution may get trapped in the local minima instead of the global minima. In order to eliminate this problem, a hybrid approach has been used where the weights of the ANN classifier are optimized by the genetic algorithm to improve accuracy. This paper shows that the results are better using the hybrid approach than the conventional approach.

E. Convolution Neural Network-Based Diagnosis

In their paper [3], Pratik et al. encourage the use of Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) as future scope, since CNN models can be used for classification of the affected skin images without the need for performing segmentation and feature extraction independently. Mobeen et al. [5] have made use of custom-made automated segmentation and have used a novel approach for implementation of the CNN methodology, where CNN has been used for feature extraction and ANN was used to classify those extracted features. The advantage of this proposed system is that CNN does not require any additional classifier like SVM, or KNN since 3 fully-connected layers were used for training the classification model. This type of classification brings its own unique benefits like it is possible to apply a back-propagation algorithm, which adjusts the parameters of neurons in all layers to obtain a better classification model.

In this paper [8], Aya Abu Ali and Hasan Al-Marzouqi have employed transfer learning by using and modifying the convolution neural network (CNN) architecture in the Light Net pretrained model to achieve higher accuracy. They classified the images without applying lesion segmentation or without using complex image pre-processing techniques. The images were pre-processed and resized to create uniformity in the sizes of all the images. Each block of the 5 blocks had a convolution, relu, pooling, and a dropout layer except for the last block where the Last block has a fully connected layer and softmax layer. They calculated the error by comparing the predicted output with the actual output.

The advantage of the proposed model presented in this paper is that it is simpler as it does not use data augmentation and uses a lesser no of parameters which is crucial in mobile applications where constraints on the size of the network and energy consumption affect the utility of developed tools. This model attains comparable results with fewer parameters. However, improved results can be obtained by using better feature extraction techniques like the ABCD rule and better image pre-processing.

The proposed system in [6] addresses 2 parts: lesion segmentation and lesion classification. The proposed solution makes use of a fully convolution-deconvolution network to segment the skin tumor from the surrounding skin. In order to address lesion classification, 2 solutions have been proposed. The first trains the dataset from scratch and the second makes use of pre-trained VGG-16. They found that the results obtained from the VGG-16 model were better than those obtained from the simple convNet architecture

F. Neuro-Fuzzy System

Bareqa Salah et al. [11] propose the use of neural networks with fuzzy logic to calculate the relevant features and

determine the type of skin cancer.

The proposed system is composed of 4 neural networks (NN). 1) NN1 determines the main type of cancer: melanoma or non-melanoma. 2) NN2 determines the type of melanoma cancer. 3) NN3 distinguishes non-melanoma skin cancer and other types of non-melanoma. 4) NN4 classifies the type of non-melanoma skin cancer. The outputs were generated between negative infinity and positive infinity instead of 0 and 1. The proposed fuzzy logic system uses the IF-THEN rules over the outputs of the neural network.

They provided the output of NN1 and NN2 as input of the first Fuzzy Logic Inference System1 (FIZ1), FIZ2 used NN1 and NN3 outputs as input data, while FIZ3 used the output of NN1, NN3, and NN4 as input.

The accuracy obtained by the neuro-fuzzy system was slightly greater than that obtained by the hierarchical Neural Network. However, the biggest disadvantage was that the increase was only found to be 0.5%.

This might be due to fewer studied images. Additionally, the proposed system classifies only melanoma and non-melanoma cancers and does not take into consideration the benign cancers.

G. Detection Using Delaunay Triangulation

In this paper [12], A. Pennisi et al. have proposed a method for Melanoma Detection Using Delaunay Triangulation. First, they have pre-processed the image to remove the hair on skin by morphological closing and then the image is equalized. The next step is detection of skin by defining boundaries in the chosen color space. The main advantage of this method is that it does not require a training phase. The next step involves extracting the contours of the lesion by edge detection using a canny edge detector. The detected edges are used as input for the Delaunay Triangulation procedure which computes a triangular tessellation of the image.

The proposed approach is highly accurate when dealing with benign lesions, while the detection accuracy significantly decreases when melanoma images are segmented. Additionally, this algorithm is highly sensitive with respect to images containing irregular borders, multiple shades of pigmentation, and varying structures and thus, it presents a lesion area that is smaller than the actual area. This behavior is the main reason why they had to consider geometrical and color features extracted from the output of the proposed algorithm as input for four different binary classifiers. However, the disadvantage of the proposed system is that it is not suitable for diagnostic applications.

H. Classification using Support Vector Machine (SVM)

SVM is used by Hiam et al. [1] to identify photos of skin

lesions as Normal or Melanoma. Image pre-processing, thresholding, statistical feature extraction with Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM), feature selection with Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and classification with Support Vector Machine are the processes included in this study (SVM). They improved the contrast of the image and used noise filtering to remove the hair cover on the skin. The ROI (region of interest) was chosen as the next stage in picture segmentation. They did thresholding, picture filling to remove background pixels from inside the object, image opening to remove additional background pixels, smoothing the contour of the object's boundaries, and ultimately cropping the image to the right size in this step. The features of asymmetry, border irregularity, energy, correlation, homogeneity, entropy, skewness, and mean were extracted next. TDS, mean, standard deviation, energy, and contrast were used to decrease the number of features to the best five: TDS, mean, standard deviation, energy, and contrast, accordingly. Lastly, classified the images as benign or cancerous using kernel SVM with radial basis function.

Using SVM, Kavitha et al. [2] obtain texture and color features for melanoma classification. The texture of an object in a photograph is an important feature that helps to identify it. Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) is used to retrieve textural features, and color histograms in several color schemes are used to detect melanoma. Color bins are formed for these histograms, and they are treated as a single feature vector. They then fed the feature vector into the SVM classifier as an input. The benefit of SVM is that it works well in high-dimensional spaces and is memory-efficient because it only needs a fraction of training points in the decision function.

I. Detection and Classification Based on Supervised and Unsupervised Learning

Ms. H. R. Mhaske et al. utilized supervised techniques such as neural networks and support vector machines, as well as the unsupervised K-mean clustering approach, to identify and characterize melanoma skin cancer in this paper. This research compares the results of three methods: k mean clustering, backpropagation neural networks, and support vector machines. The methods that they took were as follows. First, all of the photos in the dataset were subjected to image pre-processing, segmentation, and feature extraction. After then, categorization is carried out using a variety of classifiers. The classification result obtained using the k-means algorithm for unsupervised learning is 52.63 percent. The k-means algorithm divides the n data points into k clusters. When it comes to melanoma skin cancer detection, two clusters emerge one for cancer and another for non-cancer. It has been discovered that the accuracy of a Back Propagation Neural Network is 60 to 75 percent, while that of a Support Vector Machine is 80 to 90 percent. As a consequence, the research demonstrates that the Support Vector Machine outperforms the K-means clustering

technique and the Backpropagation Neural Network for the suggested system.

Table 1: Summary of related work on Skin Cancer Detection

Technique Used	Advantages	Disadvantages
Backpropagation Neural Network	Weight Adjustment	Slow convergence rate and trapping in local minima
Convolution Neural Network	Eliminates the need for performing segmentation and feature extraction independently	Time-consuming on a huge dataset
ABCD rule	Simplicity	Not useful in some cases E.g. When the diameter of the lesion is less than 6 mm
Neuro-Fuzzy System	Accurate results by providing fuzzy values instead of crisp values	---
Hybrid Artificial Neural Network and world cup optimization	Solves the shortcomings of local minima that arise in backpropagation neural network	High complexity
Hybrid genetic algorithm – Artificial Neural Network	Uses a genetic algorithm to escape local minima	----
Unsupervised algorithm – K means algorithm	Use of clusters to identify patterns. Thus, no need for labeled data	Less accuracy as compared to SVM and Neural networks
SVM	Good Accuracy	Not better than RF (Random Forest) in some cases since RF can handle categorical data, unbalanced data as well as data with missing values

CONCLUSION

We looked at a variety of non-invasive approaches for skin cancer classification and detection in this research. Pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification are all steps in the melanoma detection method.

This study examines many strategies such as the Genetic Algorithm, SVM, CNN, ABCD rule, and others. According to the assessment, each algorithm has its own set of benefits and drawbacks. Furthermore, of the methods examined, the SVM classifier has the fewest drawbacks and consequently outperforms others such as K-mean clustering and Backpropagation neural networks. We may determine from all of these existing approaches that classification based on neural network technology is superior to some others.

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